

STRATEGY FOR IMPROVING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF LEARNING ORGANIZATION IN IMPROVING ASATIDZ PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The existence of pesantren reflects their ability to become a learning organization. This ability needs to be developed in line with the decline in the performance of ustadz in pesantren. A strategy to improve the implementation of learning organization is needed. This study aims to describe the strategy of improving the implementation of learning organization to improve the performance of Asatidz at Riyadlul 'Ulum Wadda'wah Islamic Boarding School. Using the theory of strategy, organization, learning organization, management and human resource management of pesantren with a qualitative approach of case study method. The results showed that although it still needs improvement, the strategy of improving the implementation of learning organization at Condong Islamic boarding school is in accordance with the stages of supervision and evaluation from experts adjusted to government policies, pesantren culture, and based on six value systems. Various obstacles such as the lack of conceptual skills of the head of the section, the professionalism of the ustadz and the culture of quality that has not been formed, are resolved by optimizing the role of the Caretaker Assembly as SPMI Pesantren to ensure the quality of the personal mastery and team learning discipline strengthening programs.

Keywords: Strategy, Improvement, Learning Organization, Pesantren.

INTRODUCTION

The presence of pesantren in Indonesia has historically been present decades ago and still exists today. From the colonial period to post-independence, pesantren faced various stumbling blocks. The government has long provided support to pesantren, but recently passed Law No. 18/2019 on pesantren. The law is said to be the government's effort to ensure the quality and direction of pesantren policies in the future.

Instead of the quality of pesantren increasing after the juridical support from the government, the existence of pesantren does not seem to be accompanied by quality. Tasikmalaya City, which is known as the "city of santri" with 273 pesantrens, shows a less encouraging development. Many pesantren have experienced a decline, with pesantren with less than 100 students increasing sharply from 2019 to 2023. A significant increase occurred in 2019-2020 with 140 pesantren to 178 pesantren in 2021-2022. This condition continued in 2023 to 204 pesantren. The number of pesantren in Indonesia continues to increase but the increase in number is not accompanied by an increase in quality (Rabbaniya & Lina, 2020:2). The weakness of pesantren when transforming lies in the passive learning atmosphere as a result of the lack of creativity and innovation of teachers in pesantren. The ability of pesantren to adapt

and survive with formal education institutions proves that pesantren conduct learning organization to the needs of society and the environment (Ghafar, 2017:779). The discipline of learning organization refers to the structural perspective of being able to accommodate at the individual and team level to change the organization for the better (Reese, 2020:8). To create team learning, there needs to be a shared vision and the existence of talented individuals and the ability to work in effective teams is indispensable (Rebelo et al., 2020:47). Therefore, in a learning organization, the disciplines of team learning and personal mastery are interrelated. Talented teams are formed from talented individuals (Rada, 2022:100).

Both require continuous self-improvement. Team learning requires each individual to think innovatively and empower personal abilities to complement and complement each other. Therefore, the existence of pesantren will be accompanied by quality when the managers are able to encourage pesantren stakeholders to improve the discipline of team learning with personal mastery learning organization. Based on the data above, there is one pesantren that consistently survives with the number of students above 2000 people, namely Pesantren Riyadlul Ulum Wadda'wah or known as Condong Pesantren. This pesantren with a series of achievements it was established around the end of the 18th century and has the most students in Tasikmalaya City. The existence of Pesantren Condong is proof that the pesantren has succeeded in becoming a learning organization and conquering challenges from time to time. Large pesantren are not without problems. Facts in the field still found santri problems such as disciplinary violations and the achievement of Minimum Completion Criteria (KKM) for kitab subjects is only 65%. According to some sources, this is caused by the performance of asatidz.

The performance of pesantren administrators affects the discipline of santri (Zami, 2019:126). These ustadz have a strategic role in shaping the character of santri. Ustadz is a substitute for parents for students. Their presence and role are very important for the academic development and personality of students. The low performance of asatidz can be caused by various factors, both internal and external. From external factors in particular, the selection process of asatidz in the pesantren is considered not ideal because it is not in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 18 of 2019 concerning Pesantren article 34 paragraph 1 asatidz must have certain qualifications and competencies. Education and training programs and supervision of asatidz as a means of increasing personal mastery and subject teacher deliberations (MGMP) specifically for asatidz to improve asatidz team learning are not optimal.

Law number 18 of 2019 concerning pesantren as an effort to control the quality of pesantren education article 27 needs to develop an internal quality assurance system (SPMI). Based on the results of research by Tortorella et al., (2020:524) the implementation of TQM has a positive influence on learning organization. So, SPMI pesantren as a quality control group is a forum for the pesantren learning team to fix problems. The tasks of SPMI Condong pesantren include assessing the performance of asatidz. However, this performance assessment is hampered by the many tasks carried out by the SPMI team and the incomplete quality culture of the pesantren. Organizations that continuously increase the capacity to adapt to various environmental conditions, together learn from various changes so as to produce a learning organization (Senge, 1990:3). If the concept of learning organization is implemented in Islamic

boarding schools, as an indigenous institution, it can provide a place of learning for the progress of the country. Learning organization has a positive impact on one's work performance (Anggara, W.G., Febriansyah, H., Darmawan, R. and Cintyawati, 2019; Song et al., 2018).

This problem will threaten the existence of pesantren. Therefore, research is needed that examines how the strategy of revamping the implementation of learning organization in personal mastery discipline through supervision of training and supervision programs, and team learning discipline through supervision of MGMP programs and control of asatidz performance by SPMI Pesantren along with constraints and solutions in the management of each program faced by Pondok Pesantren Riyadlul 'Ulum Wadda'wah.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. Qualitative methodology is a research procedure that produces descriptive data from people and observable behavior (Bogdan:Moleong, 2007:4). The case study method is one type of qualitative research in which researchers conduct in-depth exploration of events, processes and activities of one or more people (Sugiyono, 2017:5). This study uses data triangulation as a data collection technique with informants and subjects in this study include the director of KMI, deputy director of KMI, head of the PSDM section who doubles as a team of Parenting Council, and two KMI staff asatidz at Pondok Pesantren Riyadlul 'Ulum Wadda'wah Cibeureum District, Tasikmalaya City.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Improvement strategies on the implementation of personal mastery discipline through supervision of education and training programs to improve asatidz performance.

In a learning organization, individuals and their work are seen as important factors to improve the effectiveness and performance of the institution so that each individual is required to learn continuously. The role of the boarding school is not only to transfer knowledge but also to be an agent that can transfer values as well as a guide in directing and shaping the character of students. So the quality of an ustadz to produce quality students is very necessary. To encourage this, one of them is through the development of personal mastery discipline because learning organizations facilitate the learning process for all members of the organization and continuously apply it to achieve competitive performance.

Madrasahs in developing personal mastery can be done through education and training activities, workshops, seminars in order to improve teacher performance in teaching and learning activities (Rada, 2022:74). The implementation of education and training programs in boarding schools is the right step to improve the performance of ustadz, especially performance in carrying out the teaching and learning process. From the various problems of ustadz performance found by researchers, it is necessary to improve the implementation of education and training programs. The stages of supervision of human resources in pesantren are divided into five stages, namely determining standards, determining measurements of activity implementation, measuring activity implementation, comparing standard implementation with

analyzing deviations, and taking corrections if necessary (Septuri, 2020:166). There are two education and training programs: the New Teacher Training Program (PGB) for first-year teachers and the Service Teacher Cadre Program (PKGP) for senior teachers. These programs are organized based on an analysis of education and training needs derived from performance evaluations. Program Education and training begins with a study of training needs analysis, formulation of training objectives, and curriculum design on the basis of competencies to be achieved including training materials, delivery methods, learning process for each material, time proportion, organizational methods, and training process flow (Daryanto & Bintoro, 2014:35-36).

The training program standards include objectives, goals, materials, instructors, implementation process and financing. Although the objectives of education and training programs are universal, they have been adapted to the personal formation of professional educators and qualified pedagogical skills. Teachers have an important role in the teaching and learning process at school. Educators in pesantren have more duties than educators in formal schools. Educators in pesantren have the task of caring like parents, facilitating the needs of the students, and finding solutions to the problems experienced by the students (Adhim, 2020:63). The competencies and abilities of asatidz as mentioned in Law Number 18 of 2019 concerning pesantren article 34 that educators in formal education channels must meet the qualifications and competencies of a professional educator.

Training program standards are used as a reference to assess the implementation of education and training programs. So to be able to measure the implementation of the program, a tool or method is needed. In the form of instrument for assessing the implementation of education and training programs. This is in accordance with the opinion of Handoko (2013:363) that determining measurement standard implementation activities is a way to measure the actual implementation of activities. Indicators of the success of education and training at Pesantren Condong are the implementation of all standards. From the participant aspect, it is assessed from the participation of trainees, increased knowledge, behavior change, and p o s t - t r a i n i n g program performance. As Kirkpatrick (Daryanto and Bintoro, 2014:145) to evaluate and measure the success of training using the four levels, namely reaction, learning, behavior, and results.

There is no system or tool developed to evaluate the implementation of education and training programs as a whole. Nevertheless, various findings of non-conformity from the committee are conveyed to the head of the section through verbal reports. However, measurement is still carried out on participants through post-test, pree-test, attendance of participants, activeness of asatidz and unscheduled supervision or the term muroqobah fushul. In line with the opinion of Daryanto & Bintoro (2014:151) the evaluation of education and training programs cannot be carried out only through the evaluation of the education and training program. Once best practice is to conduct multiple evaluations.

To assess discrepancies in implementation with standards, direct monitoring is carried out by the director of KMI and the person in charge of the program. There are still many discrepancies in the implementation of the program as a result of the low professionalism of human resources,

both committees and participants. Corrective action by improving the education and training implementation system is carried out to improve the quality of the program so that the performance of asatidz can continue to improve.

Improvement strategies on the implementation of personal mastery discipline through supervision of supervision programs to improve asatidz performance.

The supervision program at Pondok Pesantren Riyadlul Ulum Wadda'wah consists of two types, namely scheduled supervision and unscheduled supervision. In line with Sahertian (Suharwinnoto, 2018:27) supervision techniques with class visits can be carried out in two ways consisting of scheduled and unscheduled supervision. Limited resources, scheduled supervision is carried out as a series in the PKGP program. The assessment component in scheduled supervision consists of several aspects including learning toriqoh (learning syntax), maddah (learning material), ahwal (asatidz attitude in class), al-han (good and correct speech), and I'dad tadrīs (lesson plans).

Unscheduled supervision through the muroqobah fushul program. There is no special questionnaire in this program. Unscheduled supervision is a class visit that is carried out suddenly as Ngalim Purwo's opinion (Arikunto, 2006:54) that conducting a class visit is a visit made by both the supervisor and the principal to a class, either when the implementation of the teaching and learning process is in progress. Supervisors in the muroqobah fushul program involve senior teachers, the aspects of assessment include aspects of the discipline of asatidz in teaching including discipline in making learning tools such as i'dad tadrīs and had tadrīs, the accuracy of asatidz in starting and ending learning, the conduciveness of students, and the ethics of dress, the presence of asatidz.

The supervision program is a new innovation for pesantren, in the evaluation of the supervision program there are still some shortcomings. The evaluation of the supervision program in general has not been carried out so that it cannot be measured how much the level of achievement of the supervision program is in terms of focus, goals, objectives, time and criteria for the success of supervision. Limited time and the large number of ustadz are the main obstacles in the completion of supervision. Some of the problem findings from the monitoring results are the attendance of participants, teaching skills and the completeness of the target supervision participants.

The various findings and results of supervision recorded by the supervisor in the supervision instrument sheet are then reported to the head of the section and the head of the boarding school. The results of supervision of asatidz who are considered not meeting the criteria will later be included in education and training programs and MGMP. Follow-up of supervision results is a very crucial part related to efforts to improve the quality of learning processes and outcomes. Follow-up on the results of supervision is carried out through evaluating the results of supervision and following up on the results of supervision (Hartanto & Purwanto, 2019:28).

In following up on the results of supervision according to Hartanto & Purwanto (2019:29-30) it can take various forms such as direct coaching, indirect coaching, and situational coaching by the principal including the use of technology, the use of learning tools and media, videos,

and other tools learning, MGMP, comparative studies, and teacher performance appraisals. Follow-up on the results of supervision, especially in direct coaching, has not been implemented for every supervision participant. Special time needs to be allocated for direct coaching after supervision activities. The last stage is stabilizing the supervision instrument where supervisors and participants conduct a review to obtain a better supervision instrument. Until now, this supervision instrument has not been changed because it is considered still in accordance with the needs. The supervision instrument for *asatidz* consists of several aspects such as *toriqoh*, *maddah*, *ahwal*, *al-han*, and *I'dad tadri* (Learning Implementation Plan).

Supervision in the supervision program plays an important role in improving the personal mastery of an *ustadz*. By effectively implementing supervision in the supervision program, *ustadz* can improve their personal mastery and become more effective and inspiring teachers both for other colleagues and for students as good role models. This strategy of revamping the supervision program is in accordance with the six value systems, *pesantren* culture, and government policies.

Improvement strategies on the implementation of team learning discipline through MGMP program supervision to improve *asatidz* performance

Pondok Pesantren Riyadlul Ulum Wadda'wah in order to build team learning discipline among the *asatidz* through the Subject Teacher Deliberation Program (MGMP) specifically for *asatidz* who teach *kitab* subjects. The MGMP program initiated by the KMI section is carried out regularly once a month on Thursdays in the third week. Referring to the standard guidelines for the development of the Teacher Working Group (KKG) of Musyawarah Guru Mata Pelajaran (MGMP) from Direktorat Profesi Pendidik (2008:6) the standards for developing MGMP or KKG programs include organizational standards, program standards, management standards, facilities and infrastructure standards, human resource standards, financing standards, and quality assurance.

The MGMP program standards set focus on the preparation of plans and program implementation objectives. The purpose of the MGMP program is to equalize perceptions between *asatidz* in the process of teaching and learning activities. This perception includes the way of teaching, uniformity in achieving the material, and the variety of methods used. This goal is an indicator of the success of M G M P through the presence of participants and groups in the minutes and attendance as well as the attendance of the program. Similarity of learning outcomes for each subject.

According to Hadi et al., (2019:247) awareness of the interrelatedness or interdependence between individuals in all teams in the school organization makes each individual part of a learning society and functions as part of teamwork. The essence of team learning discipline is the ability of each member of the organization to learn together and create new knowledge collectively. *Asatidz* can learn together and solve problems that arise in the teaching and learning process at the *pesantren*. Measurement and evaluation of the implementation of the MGMP program has not yet developed a comprehensive system. The MGMP program evaluation system that runs is still monitoring the attendance and implementation of the MGMP

program both by the Director of KMI, the Board of Trustees, and the committee. However, the measurement of program implementation is through monitoring crucial and negative events. The measurement results are not administered and reported verbally. Participant absenteeism is quite high and the committee lacks a sense of responsibility. Some of them leave their duties because they have other more urgent tasks.

Non-conformities were found in the implementation of management standards, especially the attendance of participants and the lack of professionalism of the committee. To measure the success of MGMP activities and as an institution's effort to ensure the quality of MGMP implementation, according to the Direktorat Profesi Pendidik (2008:23) program administrators can "identify the achievement of predetermined standards through the appointment of a specially appointed audit team to test the fulfillment of MGMP standards". The involvement of a team that focuses on program quality assurance helps boarding schools evaluate various program deficiencies and problems that can hinder the implementation of team learning discipline.

Concrete steps to fix the problems that occur by giving warnings and warnings to MGMP participants at a special moment of evaluation with all *asatidz*. One form of improvement made by the boarding school is the formation of an organizational structure for each MGMP group, the appointment of a special person in charge of the MGMP program, and a special minutes book compiled to monitor the results of the discussions of each MGMP group.

Improvement strategies on the implementation of team learning discipline by the Unit Pesantren Internal Quality Assurance through performance control to improve *asatidz* performance

In a learning organization perspective, performance control is not only about ensuring conformance to standards, but also about learning from experience and using that knowledge to improve performance on an ongoing basis. In quality assurance procedures, according to Juran (Syarifuddin, 2014:25-26) there are three steps in quality management or better known as the Juran Trilogy, namely quality planning, control, and quality improvement.

The process of controlling the performance of *asatidz* in the leaning pesantren is carried out by forming a Parenting Assembly as an Internal Quality Assurance Unit (SPMI) in the aspect of *asatidz* and section performance. This Majelis Pengasuhan has the task of monitoring the performance of *asatidz* from the teaching aspect, the performance aspect of *asatidz* in each section, and the personal performance of *asatidz* under the supervision of student affairs. The method of controlling the performance of *asatidz* is in the form of an *asatidz* performance assessment instrument which includes aspects of learning, study, service, and violations. Adjusted to the duties and responsibilities of the *asatidz*. The output of the performance assessment is a ranking obtained from the collection of the *asatidz* task portfolio.

According to Supardi (2014:73) teacher performance can be measured through the level of teacher ability in preparing lesson plans, ability to carry out learning, carry out interpersonal relationships, carry out research on learning outcomes, enrichment, and remedial. Educator performance can be measured through their competencies. According to the Law on Teachers

and Lecturers number 14 of 2005 article 8 states that an educator must have four competencies, namely personality competence, pedagogical competence, professional competence, and social competence (Dewan Perwakilan Rakyat Indonesia, 2005:6).

Asatidz competency standards have not been specifically set by the government, in Law Number 18 of 2019 concerning pesantren, the determination of the competence of professional educators in article 34 paragraph 3 is that they can fulfill the competence of religious science or the field they teach. So that pesantren, both in developing the performance of ustadz and assessing the performance of ustadz, are required to be more creative and innovative in designing the competencies that must be possessed and creating conditions that can stimulate ustadz to learn to achieve these competencies.

The ustadz assessment instrument at Pesantren Condong is considered to have covered this and is adjusted to the duties and responsibilities that each ustadz has as an educator, aspects of learning, dedication, additional duties and code of ethics. according to Mukhtar et al. (2020:126) the performance of educators in pesantren concerns all activities shown by educators in their responsibility to educate, teach, direct and guide students in order to lead the development of students towards mental spiritual and physical biological maturity.

The performance appraisal instrument at Condong Islamic Boarding School cannot be used properly because it has failed. The current performance appraisal is based on the findings of critical events among ustadz by the care assembly. According to Nawawi (2011:256) where performance appraisal must be designed in an easy form. Seeing the very complex conditions of the pesantren, the method that is suitable for Condong pesantren is the critical incident method. Performance appraisal based on critical incidents is a recording of every employee's daily actions that have a positive or negative impact on the effectiveness of the section as a consideration for determining one's performance.

To realize a performance appraisal system that is early detection must be supported by qualified resources such as technology. Many authors suggest three approaches to learning organization practices, namely learning as a critical discourse that is not limited to managerial or organizational boundaries, learning free from performance metrics and free to explore new forms of practice (Reese, 2020:75).

Improving the quality of pesantren human resources is a long-term discourse, the management of pesantren human resources is generally not written in writing. And difficult to articulate considering that the boarding school lacks understanding in the field of administration and technology (tacit knowledge). The involvement of SPMI in performance control is an innovative strategy of Condong Islamic boarding school to explore and articulate new knowledge about asatidz performance collaboratively in strengthening team learning discipline.

The strategy of involving the SPMI team in controlling the performance of asatidz is known to have not run optimally, a strong culture of meritocracy has resulted in the delegation of performance control tasks that cannot be carried out. A leader realizing a learning organization can, among others, create an atmosphere conducive to learning, knowledge creation, and team

and individual learning, instituting mechanisms to channel and maintain creative ideas for innovation (Soeharno & Anco, 2019:202). A meritocratic culture reflects a mindset of the importance of less quality. It is important for a leader to have a commitment to quality because TQM is a top-down process. Many organizations fail because leaders lack support and commitment to quality improvement (Rahmawati & Supriyanto, 2020:3).

Evaluation and follow-up of performance control activities are only carried out on aspects of negative findings of asatidz performance. This evaluation is carried out at various routine meetings both at the boarding school level and at the section level. Follow-up on asatidz violations is in the form of participation in education and training programs, reduction in teaching schedules, task rotation, direct warning by the leadership, and returning asatidz to their parents. The role of the SPMI team in performance control has a positive impact on asatidz performance, the number of asatidz performance inequality decreases when the SPMI team conducts performance appraisals.

Obstacles in the implementation of learning organization on personal aspects mastery and team learning to improve asatidz performance

The implementation of learning organization in Condong Islamic Boarding School encountered various obstacles. The planning function of education and training programs is constrained by the lack of conceptual skills of the section heads, especially in planning the implementation time. A manager can understand all problems thoroughly by carrying out management functions including planning, organizing, implementing, and supervising (Pahlevi, Cepi; Musa, 2023:85). This obstacle will not occur if all pesantren managers coordinate the preparation of pesantren activity plans before entering the beginning of the learning year.

The lack of coordination and collaboration between section heads is an obstacle to the function of organizing education and training programs. Low professionalism has an impact on the implementation of committee duties that are not up to standard. In the implementation function, time constraints and priorities have an impact on the participation of participants in activities. So that in carrying out duties as an educator, it is often based on experience. Pesantren management In general, the old pattern of evaluating education and training programs is not thorough and poorly administered.

The implementation of the supervision program encountered various obstacles. At the planning stage, the lack of skills in managing time and coordination between sections hampered the program. At the organizing stage, the professionalism of the executive committee was considered lacking, the program implementation committee received assignments outside of supervision activities so that the implementation of supervision was not in accordance with standards. Program implementation is constrained by participant participation. The culture of quality among asatidz has not been embedded, so attendance in the supervision program is lacking. This is also an obstacle in the implementation of the supervision program evaluation. Awareness of the importance of conducting an evaluation at the end of the program has not yet become a culture.

The MGMP program encounters obstacles including MGMP program planning with incomplete standards as a result of the lack of managerial skills of the section head. In the organizing function, namely multitasking among the asatidz implementing the program as a result of the lack of coordination and communication between the heads of sections, the limited time for MGMP implementation has an impact on the commitment and consistency of asatidz to participate in the MGMP program. The culture of quality among asatidz has not been well embedded so that the control function in the MGMP program is not running well and the evaluation system has not been comprehensively formed.

Obstacles in the implementation of learning organization in the aspect of personal mastery through performance appraisal by SPMI include performance appraisal instruments in its implementation that are not yet early detection. At the organizing stage, the delegation of performance appraisal tasks cannot be implemented due to a strong culture of meritocracy. This hampers the process of assigning tasks to fostered asatidz. The implementation process is hampered by the availability of resources in terms of human resources, time, commitment and technology. The quality culture that has not yet been formed and the time constraints of the SPMI team cause a lack of time allocation to carry out program evaluation and control.

Solution in implementing learning organization in personal aspect mastery and team learning to improve asatidz performance

In general, the solution to overcome obstacles in all programs through increased coordination between sections can reduce the phenomenon of multitasking among asatidz. This will help pesantren in improving the implementation of learning organization because each human resource will focus more on what is the main task and function in each section. Improving the implementation of learning organization requires the role of leaders who are consistently present to encourage, monitor, evaluate, and develop the performance of asatidz in their sections. Through optimizing the role of leaders, it will help asatidz understand their duties and reduce obstacles in revamping the implementation of learning organization.

Management skills for section heads are very important in improving the implementation of learning organization in pesantren. Providing management training for section heads is the right solution to improve managerial skills in managing various programs, especially since conditions in pesantren are very complex. The utilization of technology in the implementation of performance evaluation and control can encourage the suitability of the system design and the process of implementing performance control by the boarding school. For example, the use of a learning management system (LMS) for book learning, the procurement of an asatidz performance assessment system, and so on. Improving organizational culture in the implementation of learning organization is very important. Important. The culture in question is a culture of meritocracy. In the pesantren environment, obeying the words of the pesantren family is highly exalted, but in the context of delegating quality assurance to assisted asatidz, it needs to be understood by all parties. Improving quality culture takes a long time and tends to be difficult to do, it can only be done with the support and consistency of a leader. Quality culture improvements carried out consistently by a leader, will be gradually followed by subordinates and slowly become a new habit that is strongly attached to the institution. To help

the success of the solution, the role of the internal quality assurance team is needed in monitoring and controlling the program to improve learning organization discipline. Quality management patterns in pesantren generally use old patterns such as program control that are not well organized. If this condition is allowed, it will certainly have an impact on the performance of asatidz. Control is closely related to quality improvement. The disciplines of team learning and personal mastery are related to each other because between the two of them require continuous self-quality improvement in the quality concept of continuous improvement known as the Quality Control Circle (QCC) or better known as the Quality Control Cluster (GKM) which requires the use of the PDCA cycle. The quality control cluster in the world of Islamic boarding schools as stated in Law No. IX. 18 of 2019 on pesantren requires pesantren to establish SPMI (Majelis Masyayikh). The SPMI team encourages the implementation of a learning organization using the PDCA cycle. This cycle was chosen as a continuous improvement step to improve the quality of programs in pesantren and in general, pesantren have not yet implemented it. The hypothetical model presented by the researcher is described as follows:

Figure 1: Model Hipotetik Sistem Integrasi Pembenahan *Learning Organization* untuk Meningkatkan Kinerja Ustadz

The pesantren internal quality assurance team encourages the PDCA cycle in improving the implementation of various programs that can improve the discipline of team learning and personal mastery in the learning organization among asatidz. Realizing a learning organization requires the role of members who constantly increase their capacity with a commitment to learning to face various changes. Activities to improve the discipline of team learning and

personal mastery in a learning organization are closely related to efforts to improve asatidz performance. The improvement strategy carried out by the SPMI team actually not only aims to improve the quality of program implementation, but in turn will improve the quality of work of asatidz in the boarding school.

CONCLUSION

This study examines how the pesantren strategy to improve the implementation of learning organization to improve the performance of asatidz at Riyadlul Ulum Wadda'wah Islamic Boarding School in Tasikmalaya City. The strategy of revamping the implementation of learning organization to improve the performance of ustadz at Riyadlul 'Ulum Wadda'wah Islamic Boarding School in Cibeureum District has been in accordance with the supervision and evaluation steps from Septuri, follow-up supervision from Hartanto and Purwanto, performance control from Juran, and management functions from G.R. Terry and based on the six value systems from Sanusi. Although it requires various improvements, the strategies implemented can help the managers of Pondok Pesantren Condong improve and improve the performance of the ustadz.

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